

ON THE FATTY ACIDS OF MARGOSA (NEEM) OIL

BY REGINALD CHILD AND WILFRED R. N. NATHANAEI.

The existence of a specific "margosic" acid, $C_{22}H_{40}O_2$, in margosa oil, claimed by Chatterjee and Sen (*Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1920-21, 8, 56) may be regarded as satisfactorily disproved by subsequent workers, although references to "margosic" acid still sometimes occur in medical literature in connection with its supposed value in the treatment of leprosy. Roy and Dutt (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1929, 48, 333r), Child and Ramanathan (*ibid.*, 1936 55, 124r) and Hilditch and Murti (*ibid.*, 1939, 58, 310r) agree that palmitic, stearic, oleic and linoleic acids account for the bulk of the component fatty acids, whilst the last two authors have further demonstrated the general make-up of the glycerides constituted from these four acids.

It is surprising that Quadrat-i-Khuda *et al.* (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 17, 189) have entered this field with a claim to have demonstrated the existence of four entirely new fatty acids, whose glycerides they say make up the bulk of margosa oil. "Earlier workers", they opine, "were misled by the physical properties of the acids because we do not find any analytical data regarding the acids from the papers of these authors".

This criticism can hardly be taken seriously. Chatterjee and Sen (*loc. cit.*) though mistaken over "margosic" acid, were satisfied that stearic and oleic acids were major components of the oil. Roy and Dutt (*loc. cit.*) separated their "solid" and "liquid" acids by rather crude methods, and certainly under-estimated the content of linoleic acid, but they did quite adequately identify the acids present. Palmitic and stearic acids were separated from the "solid" acid by the method of Hehner and Mitchell; the presence of a small percentage (0.74) of higher saturated acid was clearly shown; oleic acid was identified by conversion into elaidic acid (m. p. 42-3°, M. W. by analysis of silver salt, 283) and by oxidation to 9:10-dihydroxystearic acid, m. p. 133°; linoleic acid was identified by oxidation to tetrahydroxystearic acid, m. p. 163-65°.

Child and Ramanathan, by lead salt separation and ester fractionation, accounted for 97.6% of the total acids obtained by saponification of margosa oil. They recorded their analytical data in full, comprising saponification equivalents and iodine values of twelve "solid" ester fractions, and S.E.'s, I.V.'s and thiocyanogen values of six "liquid" ester fractions.

It should not be necessary to re-discuss the principles underlying the ester fractionation technique. These have been adequately established by Armstrong, Allen and Moore (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1925, 44, 63r) and by Hilditch (*cf. Biochem. J.*, 1934, 28, 779; "The Chemical Constitution of Natural Fats", 1940, Chapter XI), and a moderate acquaintance with the progress of fat chemistry in recent years is sufficient to show that they have justified themselves in practice. With the work of Roy and Dutt behind them and the range of their analytical data being obviously

normal, it would have been a work of supererogation for Child and Ramanathan to recover and identify the acids from their ester fractions.

However, by good fortune, the "solid" ester fractions from the work of Child and Ramanathan had been retained in this laboratory, and the present authors have had no difficulty in isolating from suitable fractions pure palmitic and stearic acids. "Liquid" fractions had not been retained, but a fresh sample of "liquid" acids was prepared from a sample of margosa oil of similar origin to that investigated in 1935. From these oleic acid was isolated semi-quantitatively as the characteristic lithium salt and converted into 9:10-dihydroxystearic acid. Linoleic acid was identified similarly as tetrahydroxystearic acid.

When this work was nearly completed there appeared a paper by Dasa Rao and Seshadari (*Proc. Indian Acad. Sci.*, 1942, 15A, 161), whom we thank for sending us a copy of their publication. These authors report a fractionation analysis on a sample of margosa oil from the Ramnad district, Andhra Province, S. India, and give figures which accord very closely with those of Child and Ramanathan (see Table I). We agree with them in supporting the suggestion of Hilditch and Murti that differences in recorded analyses may be due to climatic or varietal differences; as they point out, the climate of the Ramnad district is not very different from that of the Trincomalee district of Ceylon, whence we obtained our material. It may be noted, too, that recorded variations are consistent with the differences in iodine values (see Table I), if we neglect the figures of Roy and Dutt, who, as stated above, obviously under-estimated linoleic acid.

TABLE I

Component acids of margosa oil.

(Percentage by weight, excluding unsaponifiable matter)

	Roy & Dutt.	Child & Ramanathan.	Hilditch & Murti.	Dasa Rao & Seshadri.
	1929.	1936.	1939.	1942.
Palmitic	14.2	13.6	14.9	13.8
Stearic	24.1	19.1	14.4	18.2
Arachidic	0.8	2.4	1.3	1.8
Oleic	58.6	49.1	61.9	52.6
Linoleic	2.8	15.8	7.6	13.6
Iodine value	...	71.5	67.9	69.2
Origin of sample	...	Trincomalee.	Cawnpore.	Ramnad district.
		Ceylon.	U. P.	Andhra Prov.
			India.	S. India.

Dasa Rao and Seshadri repeated the work of Qudrat-i-Khuda *et al.*, and showed quite clearly that all the so-called "new acids" of the latter authors are

mixtures, the "A" and "B" acids containing mostly palmitic and stearic (with arachidic) acids; and their oil "X", from which were "isolated" Qudrat-i-Khuda's unsaturated acids "C" and "D", being a heterogeneous mixture still containing considerable amounts of saturated acids.

We are, with Dasa Rao and Seshadri, completely satisfied that the so-called new acids of Qudrat-i-Khuda and his colleagues are nothing more than mixtures of known acids, and that from their methods of separation nothing else could have been expected. It is not our business to account for their curious molecular weight figures for acids "A" and "C". It is sufficient to say that three separate sets of workers have now recorded ester fractionation analyses and in no case has a methyl ester fraction been obtained of a molecular weight below 270 (methyl palmitate). Ester fractionation technique would certainly have revealed as little as 2% of any acid of lower molecular weight than palmitic, had it been present. Qudrat-i-Khuda's reasons for supposing his acid "B" $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$, m.p. 55°, to be an "isomer" of palmitic acid, appear to us unconvincing as also his ascription of acid "D", $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$ to the cyclic series.

The history of fat chemistry is littered with "new" fatty acids, few of which have survived critical study. Margosa oil adds a curious chapter to this history, from Chatterjee and Sen's "margosic" acid, $C_{22}H_{40}O_2$ to Qudrat-i-Khuda's four "new" acids, $C_{14}H_{28}O_2$ and $C_{16}H_{32}O_2$, $C_{15}H_{28}O_2$ and $C_{18}H_{32}O_2$. We perhaps need hardly comment on the *a priori* improbability of the existence of the C_{15} -acid.

COCONUT RESEARCH SCHEME,
LUNUWILA, CEYLON.

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